

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Exploring informal caregivers' well-being during COVID-19 through online discussion forums

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Abstract

Background: COVID-19 has increased pressures on caregivers, disruptions to health services and increased health concerns during COVID-19. Reports have been made on informal carers' increased workload and limited support services during the pandemic.

Aims: This study aimed to explore how informal caregivers experienced their well-being during COVID-19 through online discussion forums.

Materials and Methods: A reflexive thematic analysis characterised by theoretical flexibility, organic inductive coding processes and theme development was conducted on online discussion forums. The method highlighted theme reviewing which was done twice to encourage data reflection. The project was conducted on a novel topic which was a new area of research interest. Semantic coding where participants' words were used directly in the interpretation and construction of themes was used.

Results: In the theme 'Locked in or locked away' caregivers worried about continuing care at home, due to limited freedom and worries of hiring help during a pandemic. Some expressed worries about visitation rights and grief of not being present with a loved one if they would reside in a care home. The theme 'Nothing left to give' suggested that COVID-19 exasperated caregivers' loneliness, social isolation and increased responsibilities and challenges with other roles. Bitterness, resentment and anger were felt towards lack of social support and workload. Theme 'Celebrating a virtual way of life' described how caregivers used online forums when other support services were disrupted.

Discussion: We discuss the role of informal caregiver that was described as all-encompassing during COVID-19. We highlight the importance of advanced planning for care home transitions and the use of online forums as a form of support. We suggest further exploration into informal caregivers' role balancing.

Conclusion: COVID-19 seemed to affect informal caregivers negatively, but they reframed their situations and sought online support. With COVID-19-related restrictions and increased workload, COVID-19 added an all-or-nothing aspect to care home transition decisions.

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KEYWORDS

COVID-19, discussion forum, informal caregiver, online research, respite care, thematic analysis, well-being

INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, COVID-19 began spreading globally, and by 2020, it was declared a 'public health emergency' by the World Health Organisation [1]. Many countries implemented physical distancing regulations to minimise its spread. COVID-19 has globally been associated with high records of anxiety and depression, as seen in China, while experiences of distress almost doubled in England [2, 3].

The decrease in general health also coincided with increased pressures on social and healthcare systems, with services being cancelled or postponed. This has been found to disproportionately affect women, those with chronic health conditions, and those from ethnic minority groups [4]. This impacts caregiving on two levels, one in terms of women being more likely to provide informal care [5], and second, those living with chronic illnesses are more likely to require care support. During the height of COVID-19 across Europe, provision of home care and respite opportunities within care homes were reduced or stopped [6–8]. This contributed to immediate additional pressures for informal caregivers as they aimed to answer to the gap in care needs. It has also been suggested that the lack of opportunities for respite in care homes could add to future stress when trying to navigate permanent moves to care homes [6]. In addition to limited health and social care services, there were also reports of people being reluctant to have paid carers enter their homes due to risk of COVID-19 transmission [9].

The Office of National Statistics saw an increase from 11% to 48% of the general population offering some form of caring service in April 2020 [10]. Carers UK defines an informal caregiver as an unpaid person who provides care to a family member, partner, friend or neighbour experiencing long-term physical or mental ill health, disability, or problems related to old age [11]. Other researchers recognise variations in informal caregiving activities, such as instrumental and practical support and social support and that engaging with these different types of caregiving duties does result in different health outcomes for the caregiver [12]. Informal caregivers can have poorer perceived health and well-being compared to non-caregivers [13]. There is some suggestion that informal caregivers who are older, male and who are experiencing psychological distress while supporting someone living with dementia are at greater risk of poorer physical health [14]. Others argue the gendered nature of caregiving and additional cultural

factors result in women experiencing a greater level of psychological stress [15].

Bastawrous [15] proposed understanding the impact of caregiving on the health and well-being of informal caregivers by utilising Pearlin's and Yates' stress models [16, 17] and Biddle's Role Theory [18]. Pearlin's Stress Process Model, in this context, suggests that 'caregiver burden' is a primary stressor affected by the caregiver's background and context of care [16]. When the primary stressor interacts with a secondary stressor, such as caregivers' feelings of self-esteem or role strain, this impacts the individual's well-being. Yates et al. [17] proposed caregiver 'strain' to be a secondary stressor due to primary stressors being more objective, such as number of hours spent caregiving. Secondary appraisals would then correlate with the primary stressor, and well-being would be their outcome. De Coninck et al. [7] make reference to Gérain's and Zech's [19] Informal Caregiving Integrative Model which similarly identifies the caregiving context as a contributor to caregiving stress, along with the influence of sociodemographic factors and social environment.

Role theory [18] suggests that we all play multiple social roles such as employee, or a spouse, for example. We can experience role overload when we feel we do not have enough time to contribute to these roles at the same amount as we either want to or feel expected to. Additionally, we may experience role conflict if we believe the expectations associated with certain roles exceed our expectations or capabilities [18].

As Bastawrous [15] outlined in describing the Stress Process Model [16], coping strategies and resources could help mediate the potentially negative impact of caregiving on informal caregivers. Support systems could help alleviate both primary and secondary stressors but could also reduce the risk of role overload and conflict. As already discussed, these support systems faced disruption during COVID-19, increasing the pressure on informal caregivers.

Coulson et al. found that people living with Huntington's disease mostly used discussion forums for informational and emotional support [20]. Mo and Coulson found similar uses of discussion forums for people living with HIV or AIDS [21]. Research focused on informal caregivers' use of online forums has found that informal caregivers relied on care networks online when offline care networks were impaired [22]. Tanis, Das and Fortgens-Sillman found that 'caregiver strain' decreased with active participation in online forums [23]. Due to disruptions in support services during COVID-19, it was considered likely that caregivers

would seek alternative forms of support, potentially online.

Due to increased pressures on caregivers, increased health concerns and disruption to health services, this study aimed to explore how informal caregivers' well-being was impacted by COVID-19 through observation of online discussion forums analysed using thematic analysis. This study focussed on informal caregivers who were providing care for people whose conditions were unrelated to COVID-19. Online discussion forums were utilised to avoid placing additional pressures on caregivers and due to the rationale that caregivers would be engaging more online due to limited support services.

METHODS

Design

As the aim of this research was explorative and focussed on a new area of research interest, qualitative approach was chosen to allow for participants' experiences and views to be prioritised. It was anticipated that due to a reduction in support services and increased engagement with online discussion forums for other health topics [24] that individual posts and authentic discussions between caregivers regarding their experience of well-being during COVID-19 would be present.

Sample

The data were collected from a public online discussion forum. The threads were identified by using the search terms 'COVID', 'COVID-19', 'pandemic', 'virus', 'lock-down' and 'isolation' across the forum. Threads that involved caregivers discussing their well-being during the pandemic between December 2019 and February 2021 were chosen. This resulted in data being analysed from 7 threads which included 201 posts from 183 usernames.

Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the Education and Social Sciences ethics committee (Reference number: 2020-13343-11744) in the University of the West of Scotland. Neither the discussion forums nor their users are named in this paper to protect participant anonymity. Direct quotes were used in the thematic analysis, but the quotes below have been paraphrased to protect anonymity. In line with BPS's social responsibility principle, participants were not

informed of their posts being analysed. This was done to be able to collect naturalistic data [25].

Analysis

The data was analysed using reflexive thematic analysis [26]. The reflexive approach uses theoretical flexibility and inductive data-driven coding. The quality of the analysis is conceptualised with engagement with the data and theme reviewing. The analysis utilised the six phases by Braun and Clarke [27], with a focus on semantic coding. In semantic coding, the interpretation of the data, coding and generating themes were done based on direct meanings that participants have provided. The project was initially conducted by the first author under the supervision of the second author as an undergraduate dissertation. The first author carried out the three phases of thematic analysis in conversation with the second author. This included becoming familiar with the data and generating codes and themes [27]. Before final themes were set, researchers met to review, redefine and rename them to ensure separate and distinct themes. Locating exemplars was conducted by the first author.

FINDINGS

The three themes focus on the dilemma between caregiving and care home placement, psychological effects of informal caregiving and stress-buffering aspects during COVID-19.

Theme 1: Locked in or locked away

Posts touched upon the question of whether caregiving should continue at home or whether a care facility should be considered in light of COVID-19. If at home, caregivers were responsible for the care recipient's exposure to the virus, which limited their access to external help and own freedom. If the care recipient was placed in a facility, the possibility of not seeing them again due to possible distancing restrictions was a concern. This was in response to restrictions, such as those in the UK, where care home visitations were banned from February 2020 onward [28]. This theme was divided into two subthemes, 'Care at home' and 'Care at a facility'.

Subtheme 1: Care at home

Continuing care at home was challenged by concerns around the risk of exposing a vulnerable loved one to

COVID-19 and how this restricts freedom beyond their already experienced constraints.

I can't go out with friends because I'm scared of bringing the virus home to sister.

Here the caregiver addresses increased lack of freedom and social interaction associated with the risk of exposure to COVID-19. The option of hiring help was mentioned as something that had become increasingly challenging during the pandemic.

You could hire a caregiver but you can't tell what their personal lives and views about the restrictions are like.

The above quote expresses the challenges of hiring external help due to fear of exposure to COVID-19. Socialising and hiring help were associated with concerns about greater risk of contracting COVID-19 both for themselves and their care recipient.

Caregivers described not being able to leave their homes as contracting COVID-19 from public spaces would be risky.

My care recipient is not allowed anywhere at the moment so neither am I.

Above the caregiver expresses lack of possibility to leave the house without the care recipient.

Within this subtheme, informal caregivers expressed further limitations to their freedom compared to general public during social restrictions which is focussed on the increased vulnerability their loved one is at with contracting COVID-19.

Subtheme 2: Care at a facility

The main concerns, shared by caregivers considering care homes and those who already had loved ones in care homes, revolved around social restrictions during COVID-19 and visitation bans.

This quarantine has made me worried that I will never again see my dad who lives in a care home.

Forum users expressed concerns of not being able to meet their care recipient, particularly if they were placed on upper floors, where access to meet through a window was not possible. Informal caregivers had experiences with heavy restrictions in care home visits. Some had experienced grief of not being present when their loved ones were dying.

My dad got very sick and I never was able to visit him during his last days.

These experiences often led to discussions on whether COVID-19 restrictions were worth the possibility of residents not meeting their friends and families and the consequences this had on quality-of-life residents would experience.

I don't want him to get sick but I don't want the rest of his life to be like this either.

This theme shows how informal caregivers either surrendered the remaining freedom during social restrictions, or decided to place the care recipient in a care home with the risk of not being able to see them. The transition for a care recipient moving into a facility is acknowledged as being a potentially stressful one and can result in feelings of loss for the caregiver outside of a pandemic [6, 29]. The added complexity of this decision when social restrictions were present seemed to add to this stress.

Theme 2: Nothing left to give

This theme has three subthemes: stress and exhaustion, isolation and loneliness, and feelings of bitterness, resentment, and anger.

Subtheme 1: Stress and exhaustion

Caregivers described the stressful nature of caregiving both prior to the pandemic, but also how the pandemic had intensified these feelings.

Caregiving during COVID-19 just increased the concern and the levels of responsibility. My wife is at a high risk and I would feel terrible if I contracted the virus and gave it to her.

The quote above explains why COVID-19 may add to the already stressful caregiving duties. Due to COVID-19, not only the responsibilities increased but also the risk of contracting the virus may have been a stressor itself. Beyond feelings of stress, some caregivers detailed adverse health outcomes of it.

The stress of caregiving was overwhelming and gave me mental health issues as well as problems with my physical health, such as extremely high blood pressure.

It was visible how caregivers prioritised the care recipient's health over their own time and well-being. This meant arranging their own day-to-day life according to the needs of the care recipient, which may result in them dismissing their own health needs:

I am simply doing everything in the family for multiple people. I personally haven't been able to go to a doctor and just hope my health does not deteriorate completely.

Exhaustion was communicated to be one of the key aspects of informal caregiving.

Even though I love my mom, since I started caregiving, I have been incredibly exhausted.

Within this theme caregivers expressed the impact caregiving had for them during COVID-19. Direct comments were made about their perceived health and increased levels of stress and exhaustion. Despite being aware of their health struggles, caregivers had limited time and freedom to seeking support.

Subtheme 2: Isolation and loneliness

Social isolation and loneliness have been linked to informal caregiving [30]. During the time when social restrictions associated with COVID-19 were in place this feeling continued and was exasperated. Caregiving was described as socially restrictive, and caregivers even used imprisonment as an analogy.

... I can't talk with anyone physically, go out, socialize, or even get help in caregiving because of Covid risks. I feel like a prisoner at my own home ...

Caregivers described how COVID-19 had made socialisation increasingly challenging.

Currently the UK is not in lockdown yet but we are being told to stay home. I am unsure of how I'll manage lockdown living with my dad and being so isolated from others.

It was acknowledged that the risk of COVID-19 was creating a concern about providing care in the previous theme. In this subtheme, informal caregivers felt loss of social interaction in terms of creating additional feelings of restriction and disconnection from others. This is concerning as

informal social support has been found to be directly related to physical health outcomes [31, 32].

Subtheme 3: Bitterness, anger and resentment

Resentment was a common feeling towards caregiving, especially when caregiver duties were placed upon one person.

I am still trying to get over the resentment that my health and the best years of my life were taken from me when I was taking care of my parents meanwhile my siblings completely ignored my efforts.

Caregivers addressed bitterness towards pandemic-related restrictions.

I feel angry and sometimes bitter and I express it to my mom as if she is the source of it, when instead I am frustrated of the COVID-19 restrictions and never able to get respite from her.

Within this theme forum users expressed that both the commitment needed from themselves and the involvement, or lack of, from other family members was a source of resentment. This shows that the lack of social support leads to longer impacts that can influence the future of social relationships.

Theme 3: Celebrating a virtual way of life

Even though caregivers experienced challenges, they were actively identifying positive aspects of COVID-19. This theme was categorised into two subthemes: reframing and alternative social connections.

Subtheme 1: Reframing

In this subtheme, informal caregivers expressed how COVID-19 had made aspects of their lives easier in terms of balancing different commitments. Caregivers expressed how, for example, COVID-19 had reminded people to 'slow down'.

Finally people have slowed down and learned to appreciate what really is meaningful.

It was clear how some caregivers enjoyed the lack of social pressure and easing of the 'fear of missing out'.

Now I don't have to feel guilty for staying home with dad and fear missing out on anything fun.

Here it seems as if the informal caregiver did not view the social restrictions associated with COVID-19 as an additional restriction, instead the new restrictions were creating a balance between the experiences of caregivers and non-caregivers. These new restrictions were generating a reframing around the social experience, now the caregiver was not 'missing out' because majority was not engaging in social activities.

Subtheme 2: Alternative social connections

Although not directly associated with COVID-19, another possible stress buffering factor seen across the discussion forums was the sense of community and informational support being provided among informal caregivers. Caregivers both asked and gave advice to each other.

... I feel like a prisoner at my own home, I am angry and hate myself for not being able to deal with this situation. Does anyone have tips?

Writers on the discussion forums praised how engaging with the site had helped them and recommended struggling caregivers to stay active on the site.

Stay here, this forum has been one of the biggest helpers for me during my years of caregiving. I don't feel judged or 'whiny' here, everyone just gets me and my experience. The family here allow me to 'rant' without the fear of looking like I'm just a negative person complaining, and that really helps.

The quote above shows how the forum user is able to express themselves emotionally and not be concerned about the ramifications of voicing these feelings.

Within this theme, it is evident how informal caregivers were not only acknowledging difficulties of caregiving during COVID-19 but also seeking ways to rebalance the pressures through reframing the social restrictions and seeking alternative support online.

DISCUSSION

The exploration of informal caregivers' posts on a discussion forum suggests that COVID-19 introduced new

levels of stress. One of the key stressors was the decision of whether to continue care at home or in a facility. Worries about continuing care at home included increase of caregiving duties and stress, lack of freedom and limited support. Worries about placing care recipients in facilities included visitation rights and grief of not being present with a loved one. Caregivers experienced loneliness, isolation, and challenges in balancing roles which were exasperated by the threat of COVID-19 and physical restrictions. Caregivers described bitterness, resentment and anger towards lack of social support and their workload. Some had found support from online forums when other support services were disrupted. Caregivers showed signs of coping strategies through reframing.

The theme 'Locked in or locked away' involved transitions from home to a care home, which without the complexity of a pandemic have been found to be stressful and complex for informal caregivers [6, 29]. Others have identified that while this transition can be relieving for informal caregivers, it is still emotionally draining [33]. Groenvynck et al. [33] and Samsi et al. [6] have found that caregivers can feel guilty for placing their care recipient in care home. It is now evident that COVID-19 added an 'all or nothing' – aspect to care home transition decisions.

The increased demands of caregiving were apparent in the first theme. This was also expressed in the theme 'Nothing left to give' in terms of stress and worry. Park et al. [34] studied impacts of COVID-19 on Americans and found that it changed caregiving demands and that caregivers reported stress associated with infection-related risks. Being a caregiver increased the risk of increased severity of stress and increased number of stressors. Cohen et al. [35] found that relatives of individuals with advanced dementia were stressed about the sick leave of paid caregivers, whereas family of those with milder dementia were mostly concerned about spreading the virus to the care recipient when bringing groceries. Sousa et al. [8] found that COVID-19 exasperated the stress experienced by caregivers for people living with end-stage renal disease, due to the fear of contracting COVID-19 and the life-threatening impact this would have on their care recipient but also the additional care responsibilities involved.

Caregivers were concerned about additional care responsibilities involved in order to reduce the risk of contracting COVID-19 and in filling the gaps left from discontinued professional care services. Fieselmann et al. [36] analysed German family caregivers' social media posts and found that COVID-19 had increased psychological challenges, such as depression and exhaustion. These challenges emerged, for example, from social isolation and the additional stress of not receiving professional caregiving help during the pandemic.

The reduced support from paid caregivers is seen to increase the demands on informal caregivers and limit their ability to engage in additional social roles. According to a study exploring pre-pandemic caregiving of individuals with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis by Galvin et al. demands included limited time, extra responsibilities, and restricted social life [37]. This supports the work of Vellone et al. [38] who found that quality of life of informal caregivers was improved with independence from care recipient and help in caregiving duties. In the current study and the context of COVID-19, caregivers expressed feeling 'stuck' at home with their care recipient. This is consistent with Giebel et al.'s [28] findings: caregiver roles have changed due to COVID-19 regulations and with that, social support has reduced.

Bastawrous' [15] understanding of the Stress Process Model [16] could explain the COVID-19-related strain. The regulations intensified the already demanding caregiving role (primary stressors) leading to the diminished well-being of informal caregivers, such as increased levels of stress and exhaustion (secondary stressors). COVID-19 was not simply responsible for the increase of potential stressors but also a barrier to coping strategies. Although some caregivers in this study identified that online discussion forums had the potential to mediate these negative effects and reduce role overload and conflict.

COVID-19 had limited informal caregivers' freedom as those engaging with the forums discussed limited engagement with other aspects of their life: even their own health. Therefore, the role theory [18] may not be effective in explaining the effects of COVID-19 to the informal caregivers' well-being as caregivers were not experiencing competing roles but rather a more substantial diminishing and loss of other roles than their caregiver role.

Similar to our findings, in a CarersUK survey, 44% of caregivers stated being lonely and 'cut off from people' [39]. CarersTrust investigated effects of COVID-19 on young carers and young adult carers and found that 69% of their 961 caregiver sample felt less connected to others since the pandemic [40]. When exploring Twitter feeds of family caregivers of individuals with Alzheimer's disease before and during COVID-19, Yoon et al. [41] found that loneliness became more prevalent in the tweets during the pandemic. In Essandor's systematic literature review [42] on loneliness in elderly caregivers, loneliness was found to often result from not engaging socially, grief, or lack of contacts or jobs. Vasileiou et al. [43] found that loneliness, too, was linked to limited freedom to manage own space or time and lack of spontaneity. Caregivers in their study described caregiving to be socially restrictive, and some used imprisonment as an analogy. This was also found in the current study. In line with current findings, previous research has noted how health-related worries

among caregivers may increase due to fear of spreading COVID-19 and therefore further increase social isolation [8, 9].

More useful theory to explain caregiving roles during COVID-19 could be Mead's social self [44]. Mead believed that the self emerges from social interactions, not biological factors. He argued that self-awareness and self-image are products of social experiences. During COVID-19, other social relationships were disrupted, and caregivers in our data were left with only the relationship with their care recipient. This may explain why informal caregivers may have identified with having a one, all-encompassing role and struggled with diminished identity.

Bitterness, anger, and resentment have also been identified in caregiving pre-pandemic. Feelings of bitterness and resentment in caregivers can stem from the limiting nature of caregiving duties and feelings of putting their own lives 'on hold' [45, 46]. Caregivers in Dickson et al.'s [46] study reported feelings of resentment especially when they had free time but could not fill it with desirable activities. Instead, they needed to be available for their care recipients. Loss of freedom, choice and agency were reported with sense of resentment. Because caregiving responsibilities have increased with COVID-19, absence of free time potentially affects informal caregivers' resentment.

Caregivers had found ways to reframe their COVID-19 narratives. Some experienced no longer feeling 'the fear of missing out' now that it was more socially acceptable to stay home. Even when support services were disrupted, caregivers found alternative support in online forums. Similarly, a review by Kamalpour et al. [47] found that informal caregivers used online health communities, such as discussion forums, to seek advice and provide moral empowerment. Considering the physical distancing regulations of COVID-19, online forums provided a platform that could safely be used at home. Online caregiver support can support resilience, independence, self-care, altruism, and external connections [47]. Peer support can also reduce isolation and stress [14, 48], as also suggested by the Stress Process Model [16], indicating benefits especially for informal caregivers.

Implications

These findings were significant in suggesting that caregivers were impacted by COVID-19. Prior research by Samsi et al. [6] and Davies and Nolan [29] have found advanced planning useful in care home transitions. Advanced planning can include health and social care staff working with relatives to help the care recipient settle into the care home, but also staff supporting informal caregivers in the readjustment of their caring roles [29].

Considering the first theme, importance of advanced planning is emphasised and how this can be adapted in contexts where caregivers' physical access to a care home may be limited.

We suggest that prioritising the well-being of informal caregivers during a pandemic can not only benefit them and their care recipients but also have a substantial impact on health care systems. Seeing how actively caregivers used the online discussion forum, support services could be provided in a similar form. Klemm et al. [49] found that online support groups were as effective as real-life support groups in reducing depressive symptoms and improving quality of life of informal caregivers. In their study, online groups discussed a moderator-led topic each week based on family caregiver research. Therefore, enhancing caregivers' accessibility to professionally moderated online support could be beneficial.

Critique

This study was among the first explorative studies focusing on informal caregiver well-being during COVID-19 that was not limited to caregivers of a specific condition. Both the exploration of discussion forums and the thematic analysis allowed us to explore role changes and experiences of informal caregivers that occurred during COVID-19. By exploring a platform that was convenient and safe during the pandemic, we found data on how COVID-19 affected informal caregivers beyond their already challenging roles. Caregivers seemed to identify with solely being a caregiver during COVID-19, so an exploration into caregivers' roles and role balancing would be useful.

Limitations of the study include the possibility that caregivers who were active in discussion forums may have had more challenging situations and need for support when compared to less active caregivers. As proposed by Gérard and Zech [19] in the Informal Caregiver Integrated Model and discussed by De Coninck et al. [7], it is recognised that sociodemographic, social environment and caregiving context contribute to caregiver stress. Due to the nature of extracting data from online discussion forums, this information was not fully considered. Consequently, we do not have this information regarding the users of the forums and if they were at higher risk for experiencing caregiver stress based on these factors.

We are aware that the search terms 'lockdown' and 'isolation' may have introduced a bias. This terminology in sampling can have negative connotations and lead to exclusion of countries that did not have lockdowns in place. It could also have excluded caregivers who did not

experience isolation. A different search strategy would provide more voice to this experience.

Digital poverty or the time-consuming caregiver role could also be reasons some caregivers do not use these forums. Some studies have shown that individuals in lower socioeconomic groups are more likely to provide informal care – and provide it in higher intensities [50, 51]. A study by Quashie et al. [52] suggested that socioeconomically disadvantaged individuals were more likely to provide informal care. It is unlikely that these individuals have resources to use internet-mediated support services without adequate financial support.

CONCLUSION

This study used thematic analysis to explore well-being of informal caregivers during COVID-19 from online discussion forums. COVID-19 had affected caregivers negatively, even though they cognitively reframed their situations and sought support online. Caregivers were wondering whether to continue care at home with limited support, increased workload and infection-related risks or place the care recipient in care home during COVID-19 when there was the risk of not seeing them due to physical distancing regulations. COVID-19 had exasperated loneliness and isolation and caregivers described feeling bitterness, resentment and anger towards their workload and lack of support. Future research could focus on advanced care home transition planning and caregivers' role balancing.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

This project was initially conducted as an undergraduate dissertation by the first author, with the supervision of the second author. The first three phases of the thematic analysis were conducted by the first author in conversation with the second author. The first phases were familiarization with the data and generating codes and themes [27]. Researchers met to review, redefine and rename themes before final themes were set. This was done to ensure separate themes. The first author located the exemplars. The article was written by both authors.

FUNDING INFORMATION

There was no funding for this research study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Due to the traceability of the data collected from public online forums, sharing it would be a breach of anonymity.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This study was approved by the Education and Social Sciences ethics committee (Reference number: 2020-13343-11744) in the University of the West of Scotland. The discussion forum users nor the platform are named in this paper to protect anonymity of participants. The analysis used direct quotes which were paraphrased in this report for anonymity reasons. In line with BPS's social responsibility principle, participants were not informed of their posts being analysed in order to collect naturalistic data [25].

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REFERENCES

- Sohrabi C, Alsafi Z, O'Neill N, Khan M, Kerwan A, Al-Jabir A, et al. World Health Organization declares global emergency: a review of the 2019 novel coronavirus (COVID-19). *Int J Surg*. 2020;76:71–6.
- Li J, Yang Z, Qiu H, Wang Y, Jian L, Ji J, et al. Anxiety and depression among general population in China at the peak of the COVID-19 epidemic. *World Psychiatry*. 2020;19(2):249–50.
- Smith LE, Amlôt R, Fear NT, Michie S, Rubin GJ, Potts HWW. Psychological wellbeing in the English population during the COVID-19 pandemic: a series of cross-sectional surveys. *J Psychiatr Res*. 2022;153:254–9.
- Topriceanu C-C, Wong A, Moon JC, Hughes AD, Bann D, Chaturvedi N, et al. Evaluating access to health and care services during lockdown by the COVID-19 survey in five UK national longitudinal studies. *BMJ Open*. 2021;11(3):e045813.
- del -Pino-Casado R, Frías-Osuna A, Palomino-Moral PA, Ramón Martínez-Riera J. Gender differences regarding informal caregivers of older people. *J Nurs Scholarsh*. 2012;44(4):349–57.
- Samsi K, Cole L, Manthorpe J. “The time has come”: reflections on the “tipping point” in deciding on a care home move. *Aging Ment Health*. 2021;19:1–7.
- De Coninck D, Van Doren S, Matthijs K, De Clercq A. Informal care burden during the COVID-19 pandemic in Flanders, Belgium: the role of perceived threat, personality and resilience. *Scand J Caring Sci*. 2023;37(3):350–63.
- Sousa H, Frontini R, Robeiro O, Paúl C, Costa E, Amado L, et al. Caring for patients with end-stage renal disease during COVID-19 lockdown: what (additional) challenges to family caregivers? *Scand J Caring Sci*. 2022;36(1):215–44.
- Kent EE, Ornstein KA, Dionne-Odom JN. The family caregiving crisis meets an actual pandemic. *J Pain Symptom Manage*. 2020;60(1):e66–9.
- Office for National Statistics. Coronavirus and the impact on caring [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2022 Dec 17]. Available from: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/healthandsocialcare/conditionsanddiseases/articles/morepeoplehavebeenhelpingothersoutsidetheirhouseholdthroughbecoronaviruscovid19lockdown/2020-07-09>
- Carersuk. Facts about carers 2019 [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2021 Oct 17]. Available from: <https://www.carersuk.org/briefings/facts-about-carers-2019/>
- Siira E, Olaya-Conreras P, Yndigegn S, Wijk H, Rolandsson B, Wolf A. Older adults' provision of informal care and support to their peers – a cornerstone of Swedish society: demographic characteristics and experience of social isolation. *Scand J Caring Sci*. 2022;36(2):468–81.
- Berglund E, Lytsy P, Westerling R. Health and wellbeing in informal caregivers and non-caregivers: a comparative cross-sectional study of the Swedish general population. *Health Qual Life Outcomes*. 2015;13(1):1–11.
- Pinquart M, Sörensen S. Correlates of physical health of informal caregivers: a meta-analysis. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*. 2007;62(2):126–37.
- Bastawrous M. Caregiver burden – a critical discussion. *Int J Nurs Stud*. 2013;50(3):431–41.
- Pearlin II, Mullan JT, Semple SJ, Skaff MM. Caregiving and the stress process: an overview of concepts and their measures. *Gerontologist*. 1990;30(5):583–94.
- Yates ME, Tennstedt S, Chang BH. Contributors to and mediators of psychological well-being for informal caregivers. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*. 1999;54(1):12–22.
- Biddle BJ. Recent development in role theory. *Annu Rev Sociol*. 1986;12:67–92.
- Gérain P, Zech E. Informal caregiver burnout? Development of a theoretical framework to understand the impact of caregiving. *Front Psychol*. 2019;31(10):1748.
- Coulson NS, Buchanan H, Aubeeluck A. Social support in cyberspace: a content analysis of communication within a Huntington's disease online support group. *Patient Educ Couns*. 2007;68(2):173–8.
- Mo PKH, Coulson NS. Are online support groups always beneficial? A qualitative exploration of the empowering and disempowering processes of participation within HIV/AIDS-related online support groups. *Int J Nurs Stud*. 2014;51(7):983–93.
- Menke M, Wagner AJ, Kinnebrock S. Communicative care in online forums: how burdened informal caregivers seek mediated social support. *Int J Commun*. 2020;14:1662–82.
- Tanis M, Das E, Fortgens-Sillmann M. Finding care for the caregiver? Active participation in online health forums attenuates the negative effect of caregiver strain on wellbeing. *Communications*. 2011;36(1):51–66.
- Biester L, Matton K, Rajendran J, Provost EM, Mihalcea R. Quantifying the effects of COVID-19 on mental health support forums [Internet]. *ArXiv*. 2020;9 [cited 17 Dec 2022]. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.04008>
- British Psychological Society, Hewson C, Buchanan T. Ethics guidelines for internet-mediated research [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2021 Oct 17]. Available from: <https://www.bps.org.uk/guideline/ethics-guidelines-internet-mediated-research>
- Braun V, Clarke V. Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qual Res Sport Exerc Health*. 2019;11(4):589–97.
- Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol*. 2006;3(2):77–101.
- Giebel C, de Boer B, Gabbay M, Marlow P, Stoop A, Gerritsen D, et al. “Because if I don't hold his hand then I might as well not be there”: experiences of Dutch and UK care home visiting during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Int Psychogeriatr*. 2021;35:107–16.

29. Davies S, Nolan M. "Making the move": relatives' experiences of the transition to a care home. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2004;12(6):517–26.
30. Hajek A, Kretzler B, König HH. Informal caregiving, loneliness and social isolation: a systematic review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(22):12101.
31. Williams SW, Williams CS, Zimmerman S, Munn J, Dobbs D, Sloane PD. Emotional and physical health of informal caregivers of residents at the end of life: the role of social support. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*. 2008;63(3):S171–83.
32. Hernández-Padilla JM, Ruiz-Fernández MD, Granero-Molina J, Ortíz-Amo R, López Rodríguez MM, Fernández-Sola C. Perceived health, caregiver overload and perceived social support in family caregivers of patients with Alzheimer's: gender differences. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2020;29(4):1001–9.
33. Groenvynck L, de Boer B, Beaulen A, de Vries E, Hamers JPH, van Achterberg T, et al. The paradoxes experienced by informal caregivers of people with dementia during the transition from home to a nursing home. *Innov Ageing*. 2022;6(Suppl 1):23.
34. Park CL, Russell BS, Fendrich M, Finkelstein-Fox L, Hutchison M, Becker J. Americans' COVID-19 stress, coping, and adherence to CDC guidelines. *J Gen Intern Med*. 2020;35(8):1–8.
35. Cohen G, Russo MJ, Campos JA, Allegri RF. Living with dementia: increased level of caregiver stress in times of COVID-19. *Int Psychogeriatr*. 2020;30:1–5.
36. Fieselmann J, Wahidie D, Yilmaz-Aslan Y, Brzoska P. Additional burdens of family caregivers during the Covid-19 pandemic: a qualitative analysis of social media in Germany. *Nurs Health Sci*. 2022;24(2):414–22.
37. Galvin M, Corr B, Madden C, Mays I, McQuillan R, Timonen V, et al. Caregiving in ALS – a mixed methods approach to the study of burden. *BMC Palliat Care*. 2016;15(1):81.
38. Vellone E, Piras G, Talucci C, Cohen MZ. Quality of life for caregivers of people with alzheimer's disease. *J Adv Nurs*. 2008;61(2):222–31.
39. Carers UK. Caring behind closed doors: six months on [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2022 Dec 17]. Available from: <https://www.caringtogether.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Caring-behind-closed-doors-Oct20-Carers-UK-PDF.pdf>
40. CarersTrust. Our survey on the impact of coronavirus on young carers and young adult carers [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2021 Oct 17]. Available from: <https://carers.org/what-we-do/our-survey-on-the-impact-of-coronavirus-on-young-carers-and-young-adult-carers->
41. Yoon S, Broadwell P, Alcantara C, Davis N, Lee H, Bristol A, et al. Analyzing topics and sentiments from twitter to gain insights to refine interventions for family caregivers of persons with alzheimer's disease and related dementias (ADRD) during COVID-19 pandemic. *Stud Health Technol Inform*. 2022;14(289):170–3.
42. Essandor NY. Loneliness in the elderly family caregiver [degree thesis in human ageing and elderly service]. Helsinki (FI): Arcada 2012.
43. Vasileiou K, Barnett J, Barreto M, Vines J, Atkinson M, Lawson S, et al. Experiences of loneliness associated with being an informal caregiver: a qualitative investigation. *Front Psychol*. 2017;8:585.
44. Mead GH. The social self. *J Philos Psychol Sci Methods*. 1913;10(14):374–80.
45. Lund M. Caregiver, take care. *Geriatr Nurs*. 2005;26(3):152–3.
46. Dickson A, O'Brien G, Ward R, Allan D, O'Carroll R. The impact of assuming the primary caregiver role following traumatic spinal cord injury: an interpretative phenomenological analysis of the spouse's experience. *Psychol Health*. 2010;25(9):1101–20.
47. Kamalpour M, Rezaei Aghdam A, Watson J, Tariq A, Buys L, Eden R, et al. Online health communities, contributions to caregivers and resilience of older adults. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2020;29(2):328–43.
48. Cohen S, Wills TA. Stress, social support, and the buffering hypothesis. *Psychol Bull*. 1985;98(2):310–57.
49. Klemm PR, Hayes ER, Diefenbeck CA, Milcarek B. Online support for employed informal caregivers. *CIN. Comput Inform Nurs*. 2014;32(1):10–20.
50. Saito T, Kondo N, Shiba K, Murata C, Kondo K. Income-based inequalities in caregiving time and depressive symptoms among older family caregivers under the Japanese long-term care insurance system: a cross-sectional analysis. *PloS One*. 2018;13(3):e0194919.
51. Tokunaga M, Hashimoto H. The socioeconomic within-gender gap in informal caregiving among middle-aged women: evidence from a Japanese nationwide survey. *Soc Sci Med*. 2017;173:48–53.
52. Quashie NT, Wagner M, Verbakel E, Deindl C. Socioeconomic differences in informal caregiving in Europe. *Eur J Ageing*. 2021;19(3):621–32.

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